

Acceptability of Made in Nigeria Packaged Food Products

Ichekor, O.

Department of Vocational Education, Delta State University, Abraka Nigeria
tegalichekor@gmail.com

D. O. Arubayi (PhD)

Department of Vocational Education, Delta State University, Abraka Nigeria
arubayido@delsu.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study examined consumer's acceptability of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Five research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the survey method and an Ex-post Facto Research Design. The population of the study comprised all consumers above the age of 15 years who reside in Delta State. The researchers randomly sampled 384 individuals. The researchers used questionnaire to collect data in this study. The face and content validities of the questionnaire were determined by experts. Cronbach alpha reliability index was used to determine the internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Mean, standard deviation and Pearson's correlation coefficient of determination were used to answer the research questions. Independent samples t-test and Pearson's product correlation coefficient were used to test hypotheses 2-4 at .05 level of significance. The findings revealed that the extent to which Nigeria packaged food products are acceptable to consumers is high; that attitude, location and educational level can influence consumers' acceptance of such packaged food products; The finding also revealed that gender can barely influence consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Based on these findings, the following recommendations were made: that producers should continuously innovate and expand the range of Nigeria packaged food products to meet diverse consumer preferences and capture a larger market share.

Keywords: Made-in-Nigeria; Packaged Food Products; Acceptability; Consumers

Introduction

The issue of diversification of the Nigerian economy has been one areas of focus, especially by the present administration of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu. One of the keys to the actualisation of such noble idea is consumers' acceptance of made-in-Nigeria goods. A consumer is the actual and potential buyer/user of a product. According to the Fair-Trading Act (as cited in Jacob-Obi, 2018), a consumer is any person for whom services are sought to be supplied in the course of a business carried on by the person supplying or seeking to supply them and who does not receive or seek to receive the goods or services in the course of a business carried on by him. Arubayi (2009) defined a consumer as someone who buys and uses goods and services to satisfy personal household needs. This simply imply that everyone at one point in time, is a consumer. Ukpore (2009) further defined a consumer as someone who is conscious of his values and is competent enough to establish priorities by making coherent choices on goods and services.

A consumer is an individual who purchases goods and services for personal use. Someone who can make a decision whether or not to patronise an item at a particular shop. A consumer can also be regarded as someone who can be influenced by marketing and advertisement. Kanyip (2001) defined a consumer as a hirer, a buyer, a patient, a client, a sailor, an hotel guest, a bank customer, an insured or policy holder and indeed all end users of goods and services. This simply means that consumers are not just individuals who purchase goods, but also extend to individuals who subscribe and pay for services. The end-users of products and/or services, because they are the end-users of products and/or services, their acceptance of such products and services are issues that should be in the front burner of every debates by major stakeholders of the Nigerian economy. This is the thought of Arubayi (2009), when she stated that "the opinion of those who eat the dinner should be considered if we want to know how it tastes". This is why a study of consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State became necessary.

Consumer acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products is the extent to which consumers are willing to patronise Nigeria packaged food products. It entails consumers' general behaviour towards Nigeria packaged food products, which include their attitude, appreciation and use of such products. Birol and Bouis (2019) defined consumer acceptance as an integrated index of the subjective preferences of consumers for the products and depends on organoleptic properties, safety, marketing, and cultural hesitation regarding the use of new materials. The issue of product acceptability is very apt for what it means. With acceptability, an organization's product receives repeat sales. With repeat sales; profits are made, ploughed back and which facilitates growth/expansion and possible diversification. With this, organizational mission, goals and objectives are realized (Okafor, 2007).

One of the major national goals in Nigeria is to have a self-reliant Nation. The implication of this goal is that Nigeria as a Nation should be able to produce whatever that is needed by the citizenry. Goods produced within Nigeria are called Made-in-Nigeria goods. Buhari and Aliyu (2017) defined made-in-Nigeria goods as goods manufactured in Nigeria by

indigenous manufacturing companies based in Nigeria using mainly locally sourced materials. From inception, there have been goods locally processed or manufactured in Nigeria. In fact, Nigeria produces vast array of packaged food products.

Packaged foods may be defined as any food offered for retail sale, other than raw food and food served, sold, or provided ready to eat in any shop. Such food include flour, sugar, beverages, tinned foods, among others. The European Directive on Packaging and Packaging Waste (2000) defined packaged foods in two ways; in terms of protective role and in business terms. In terms of protective role, they defined food packaging as a means of achieving safe delivery of products in sound condition to the final user at a minimum cost. On the other hand, they defined food packaging in business terms as ‘a techno-economic function for optimising the costs of delivering goods whilst maximising sales and profits. It also refers to any material used in wrapping and protecting goods from harsh climatic conditions and contaminants.

Food packaging is part of mankind’s history, and now more than ever packaging technology is used to enable food to travel safely over long distances and still be healthy and nutritious at the time of consumption (Marsh & Bugusu, 2007). Packaging is the combination of food science, processing, and preservation. In modern society, the principal functions of food packaging are to protect the food from external damage and contamination, contain the product to allow for transport, and provide information about the package contents to consumers. Food packaging can delay and protect food from chemical, biological, and physical deterioration, extend shelf-life, maintain, increase, and assure the quality and safety of products. Packaging also provides biological protection against microorganisms, insects, rodents, and other animal pests, and physical protection of the food product against mechanical damage, shock, and vibrations during transport and distribution.

Packaging is used in effective storage, as material handing tool, a convenience item, a cost-saving device, a preservative, a processing aid and of course, as an effective marketing tool. This plays a key role in the presentation of food items to the end-user or consumer. It gives the product its unique identity and individuality. For instance, an average Nigerian consumer would always identify the world-famous coca cola soft drink, with the shapely, transparent glass bottle, the lager beer with the green bottle and the tomato puree with the lacquered tin.

The Nigerian government since 1994 has been taking steps to encourage favourable patronage of made-in-Nigeria goods. In a bid to stem the tide of foreign domination of the nation’s economy, the government promulgated the Nigerian Enterprises Promotion Decree in 1972. The basis of this decree was to reduce foreign dominance on the economy, encourage local retention of profits, and create employment opportunities amidst other objectives. Notably, despite this laudable efforts of the government, acceptance of made-in-Nigeria goods seems very low. Olakunori (2002) confirmed that there is too much preference for foreign made goods in Nigeria as a result of the citizen’s lingering colonial mentality and inferiority complex, which resulted to the importation of manufactured packaged food products. The preference among Nigerians for foreign made goods is both alarming and disturbing especially when considered in the light of its effect on local industries. There is an assumption among some

Nigerians that locally made goods are inferior to imported and foreign made goods in terms of quality and performance to the extent that some local manufacturers have resorted, in a bid to remain relevant, to claiming a foreign origin for their products.

This practice may cause great deficiency in the Nigerian manufacturing industries in both demand deficiency and structural form (Agbonifoh, et al., 2007). Ogumbe (2001) opined that the manner with which Nigerians discriminate between locally manufactured goods and foreign made goods is very amazing. He further states that although Nigeria produces building materials, consumer goods, miscellaneous items like chemical drugs, drinks, cooking utensils and stationary items, their preference for foreign-made goods are high. These items are often called “made-in- Nigeria goods” or “the Igbo made” by so many Nigerians as a result, these products receive little or no patronage by them. With this attitude towards “made in Nigerian goods” Nigeria loses its craftsmanship, local production, regression in export, drawback in technology and finally poor economic growth. In the long run, some Africans (Nigerians in particular) seem poor since people tend to ignore even their traditional simple techniques of producing goods which they inherited from their forefathers in favour of the foreign goods (Walter Rodney, as cited in Buhari & Aliyu, 2017).

Ekeng and Ewah (2010) buttressed that many companies in major commercial cities have been shut down due to dwindling sales as a result of buyers’ preference for foreign made similar products as against local brands. This may have resulted to the laying-off of workers, thereby adding to the number of unemployed in the country. Moreover, some of these retrenched and frustrated workers in most cases may constitute social problem to the society at large. If industrial growth and sustainability is not encouraged through acceptance and patronage of locally made goods, the economic prospects of the country may be in shambles and investment culture especially within the private sector may be in doubt. This issue may have led to the poor economic foundation of Nigeria during the colonial days. Observably, the imperialist government seemed to have encouraged the buying of their manufactured goods and have taken away Nigeria’s raw materials (in the form of export) at prices below their cost value. Thus, the imperialist government seem not to have encouraged the need for Nigeria to have industries that could produce similar goods as Nigeria was a ready market for their products. Over importation and dependence on foreign made goods may have led to the indirect devaluation of the naira, capital transfer, low per capita income, dumping of goods, among other economic vices. If consumers are encouraged to buy at least reasonable quantity of the locally produced goods, it will minimize the problem of poor economic growth and more wealth will be created for capital project, infrastructural facilities and job creation.

Statistical data from previous years showed that Nigerian’s import for consumer goods has been increasing over time, in spite of the efforts of the government on the prohibition of the import of consumers’ goods with some exceptions. For instance, Nigeria now diverts greater part of the Nation’s income for importing foreign made goods as a result of the increasing demand (Buhari & Aliyu, 2017). Data released from by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2014) showed that Nigeria’s food import bill rose from mere ₦112.88million annually during 1970–1974 to ₦1,964.8million in 1991 while between 2000 and 2008, the sum of

₦180billion (or so) was spent on importation of cheap grains. The data further showed that imports between 2009 and 2012 stood at 30%, 17.4%, 21.5%, and 12.9% respectively (CBN, 2014). Thus, there was decline in export in crop production, while food production increased only marginally. According to Buhari and Aliyu (2017), importation syndrome may have impact on the Nigerian economy; including the loss of indigenous skills, decline in the level of national income and a total collapse of the indigenous industries. For instance, most of the food items (such as flour, sugar, beverages, tinned foods, among others) imported into the country could be produced locally even at relatively cheaper rate.

Several reasons may have been responsible for the poor consumer's acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products. The researchers assumes that attitude, educational level, sex and location may be responsible. Odiogor (2007) identified attitude towards foreign goods by Nigerian consumers and described Nigerians as indiscriminate consumers who lack pride in themselves, their competence, abilities and in anything that they produce. Armed with this mental attitude, companies that do businesses in Nigeria go all out to import raw materials and develop strategies to enforce compulsive consumption habit on consumers. An average consumer in Nigeria would brag about the number of foreign products in their collection, while disparaging a similar product from a local source, even when there is hue and cry that products from South East Asia are hardly durable. In most cases, some of these products are produced under the specification of unscrupulous Nigerian importers looking for fast profit, yet, buyers still embrace and buy these products without the slightest form of discrimination. The reason for the high level of unemployment, the depressed manufacturing sector and sprawling poverty in the country may be linked to the preference for foreign made goods to those made in Nigeria which may be to the detriment of our country's economic stability. Other variables which may influence people's acceptance of one good and/or service for another such as education, gender and attitude.

Educational level determines people's social strata and this culminate in their buying propensity in terms of preference for foreign goods. How much a consumer has in terms of purchasing power may not determine the social class of such consumers but the level of awareness consumers have on purchasing superior and durable goods. These superior and durable goods or commodities can be ascertained if consumers are knowledgeable and well informed on the authenticity of goods or commodities. Therefore, the researchers assumes that educational levels can predict how informed male and female consumers are when it comes to preference for foreign goods in Nigeria.

Gender may have an important role in consumer behaviours, there are differences between men and women about expectations, wants, needs, life-style, among others. reflect in their consumption behaviours. Men and women really do have fundamentally different set of characteristics. Each sex has a firmly entrenched characteristics with women showing more sensitivity, warmth and apprehension towards certain goods and services than men. Both men and women in urban and rural locations may vary in their acceptance of certain packaged food products.

Urban and rural locations can also influence consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products. For instance, in urban areas, residents typically have better access to information through media, the internet, and social networks. They are more likely to be aware of a broader range of products, including those that are locally made. This awareness can lead to a greater acceptance of locally made products. In rural areas, access to information may be limited, which can result in less exposure to locally produced goods. Economic disparities between urban and rural areas play a crucial role. Urban consumers often have higher disposable incomes, which may make them more open to trying new products, including local ones. In contrast, rural consumers may have more limited budgets and may be more price-sensitive. Locally made products might need to be competitively priced to gain acceptance in rural areas.

In rural areas, there can be a strong attachment to traditional and locally made products. Rural consumers might have a preference for items made by local artisans or using traditional methods. In contrast, urban consumers may be more exposed to global brands and trends, which can influence their preferences. Urban consumers often have access to a wider range of products and services, which can lead to higher expectations for quality. Locally made products may need to meet these expectations to gain acceptance in urban areas. In rural areas, where there might be fewer choices, consumers may be more willing to accept locally made products if they meet basic quality standards.

Urban areas typically have better infrastructure and distribution networks. Locally made products may be more accessible in urban locations, influencing consumer choices. In rural areas, limited distribution channels and transportation challenges can make it harder for locally made products to reach consumers, reducing their acceptance. Urban areas often have more sophisticated marketing and branding opportunities. Effective marketing can create a sense of desirability for locally made products. In rural areas, where marketing resources might be limited, word-of-mouth and local community endorsements can be more influential. Urban consumers are often more aware of environmental and social issues. They may be more inclined to support locally made products to reduce the carbon footprint associated with transportation and to promote local economies. This can positively impact the acceptance of locally made products in urban areas. Government policies and incentives can also play a role. In some cases, governments may promote the consumption of locally made products through programs and incentives, which can impact acceptance in both urban and rural areas.

Enhancing consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products involves a combination of strategies. For instance, ensuring that the quality of locally made products meets or exceeds industry standards. Seeking relevant certifications to demonstrate the quality and safety of products. Being transparent about the sourcing of ingredients and the production process. Highlighting the local origins of the ingredients and provide information about how the products are made. Transparency can build trust with consumers. Differentiating products in terms of taste, quality, and uniqueness. Highlighting the unique aspects of your locally made products that set them apart from mass-produced alternatives. Emphasizing the use of local

ingredients and the support of local farmers or producers. This can create a sense of community involvement and pride in supporting local businesses.

Sharing the story behind brand and products. People connect with narratives, so tell the story of your business, its mission, and the people behind the products. This humanizing brand and builds a personal connection with consumers. Educating consumers about the benefits of supporting locally made products, such as reducing environmental impact, boosting the local economy, and preserving local traditions. Organizing sampling events at local markets, fairs, or supermarkets. Let consumers taste your products. Once they experience the quality and taste, they are more likely to purchase.

From the above discussion, consumer acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products seems to be poor. Therefore, the researchers aims to examine the extent of consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent are Nigeria packaged food products acceptable to consumers in Delta State?
2. What is the influence of attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products on consumers' acceptance of such packaged food products in Delta State?
3. What is the influence of location on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State?
4. What is the influence of educational level on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State?
5. What is the influence of gender on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in the study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the acceptance of packaged food products between urban and rural consumers in Delta State
2. There is no significant relationship between attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products and their acceptance among consumers in Delta State
3. There is no significant relationship between educational level and their acceptance of made-in-Nigeria foods among consumers in Delta State
4. There is no significant relationship between gender and acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products among consumers in Delta State

Methods

This study used survey method and an *Ex-post Facto* Research Design. The population of the study was made up of all consumers above the age of 15 years who reside in Delta State. For the purpose of the study, the researchers randomly sampled 384 individuals from the three Senatorial Districts of Delta State. The researchers relied on the recommendation of Krejcie

and Morgan (1970) to determine the sample size. In their study of sample size determination, they recommended that when a given population is above 1000,000, that a sample size of 384 is adequate for a research activity (see Appendix I). For even distribution the researchers selected 128 respondents from each of the three senatorial districts, using Cluster Random Sampling Technique.

The researchers used questionnaire to collect data in this study. The questionnaire contained two sections; 1 and 2. Section 1 of the questionnaire elicited the demographic data of the respondents such as gender, location and educational level. Section 2 contained sub-section A, which is on Consumer's Acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products; sub-section B is on the Attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products; All the items on sub-section A to D were each on a four-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE = 4), High Extent (HE = 3), Low Extent (LE = 2) and Very Low Extent VLE = 1). The researchers gave the instrument to three experts in the field of Home Economics, who determined the face and content validity of the instrument. For clarity, relevance, appropriateness of the instruments for data collection based on the purpose of the study, research questions and hypotheses, the experts made useful corrections, modifications and suggestions, from which a final copy of questionnaire was made. The researchers conducted a pilot study by administering the questionnaire to consumers in Edo State, which is different from the location of the study to estimate the reliability of the instrument. The data obtained were subjected to a reliability test. The researchers used Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient, which produced a measure of internal consistency. The reliability study produced the following coefficients: Consumer's Acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products = 0.95; and Attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products = 0.96.

The researchers personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents. They recruited and briefed five research assistants, who helped them with the administration. The researchers sought and obtained the consent of the respondents for ethical reasons. They also assured the respondents that the process was voluntary and that they were free to accept or decline to participate in the study. The researchers administered and retrieved the copies of the questionnaire on the spot. The researchers used several statistical tools to analyse the data. The researchers used mean scores and standard deviation with a benchmark of 2.50 (based on the 4-point scale) to answer research questions one. Pearson's correlation coefficient of determination was used to answer research questions two, three, four and five. Independent samples t-test was used to test hypothesis 1. Pearson's product correlation coefficient was used to test hypotheses 2-4. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent are Nigeria packaged food products acceptable to consumers in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean analysis of the extent to which Nigeria packaged food products are acceptable to consumers in Delta State

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	I accept made-in-Nigeria packaged foods	3.65	0.69	High
2.	I prefer made-in-Nigeria packaged foods to foreign packaged foods	3.38	0.74	High
3.	I will be willing to buy made-in-Nigeria packaged foods if the price is lower than foreign goods	3.38	0.85	High
4.	My friends love to eat made-in-Nigeria packaged food	3.33	0.91	High
5.	I don't mind buying made-in-Nigeria packaged foods even if they are more expensive	3.28	0.93	High
6.	I believe made-in-Nigeria packaged foods are of superior quality	3.25	0.85	High
7.	I often purchase made-in-Nigeria packaged foods	3.24	0.86	High
8.	In my home, we eat made-in-Nigeria packaged foods all the time	3.23	0.89	High
9.	I will recommend made-in-Nigeria packaged foods to my friends to buy	3.22	0.87	High
Grand Mean		3.33	0.84	High
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Table 1 shows the mean analysis of the extent to which Nigeria packaged food products are acceptable to consumers in Delta State. From the result, the mean score ranged from 3.22 to 3.65 with a grand mean of 3.33. The criterion mean used for the assessment is 2.50, which indicates the extent to which Nigeria packaged food products are acceptable to consumers in Delta State is high. Indication is that they accept made-in-Nigeria packaged foods, prefer made-in-Nigeria packaged foods to foreign packaged foods, are willing to buy made-in-Nigeria packaged foods if the price is lower than foreign goods among others.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products on consumers' acceptance of such packaged food products in Delta State?

Table 2: Pearsons' Correlation and Coefficient of Determination on the influence of attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products on consumers' acceptance of such packaged food products in Delta State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	Remark
Attitude		3.19	0.52				High Influence
Acceptance	384	3.33	0.60	0.659	0.434	43.4	

In Table 2, the researchers presented the result of a Pearson's correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the influence of attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products on consumers' acceptance of such packaged food products in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.659$, $r^2 = 0.434$ and $r^2\% = 43.4$. The result implies that attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products can influence consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products

contributes 43.4% variability to consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of location on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State?

Table 3: Pearsons' Correlation and Coefficient of Determination on the influence of location on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State

Variable	<i>n</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²	<i>r</i> ² %	Remark
Location		1.23	0.42				Low Influence
Acceptance	384	3.33	0.60	0.270	0.073	7.3	

In Table 3, the researchers presented the result of a Pearson's correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the influence of location on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.270$, $r^2 = 0.073$ and $r^2\% = 7.3$. The result implies that location can influence consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Location contributes 7.3% variability to consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State.

Research Question 4: What is the influence of educational level on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State?

Table 4: Pearsons' Correlation and Coefficient of Determination on the influence of educational level on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State

Variable	<i>n</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²	<i>r</i> ² %	Remark
Educational		4.08	1.33				Low Influence
Level	384			0.199	0.040	4.0	
Acceptance		3.33	0.60				

In Table 4, the researchers presented the result of a Pearson's correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the influence of educational level on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.199$, $r^2 = 0.040$ and $r^2\% = 4.0$. The result implies that educational level can influence consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Educational level contributes 4.0% variability to consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State.

Research Question 5: What is the influence of gender on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State?

Table 5: Pearsons' Correlation and Coefficient of Determination on the influence of gender on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State

Variable	<i>N</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²	<i>r</i> ² %	Remark
Gender		1.67	0.47				Low Influence
Acceptance	384	3.33	0.60	0.066	0.004	0.4	

In Table 5, the researchers presented the result of a Pearson's correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the influence of gender on consumers' acceptance

of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.066$, $r^2 = 0.004$ and $r^2\% = 0.4$. The result implies that gender can barely influence consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Gender only contributes 0.4% variability to consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the acceptance of packaged food products between urban and rural consumers in Delta State

Table 6: t-test comparison of urban and rural consumers in the acceptance of packaged food products in Delta State

Location	n	Mean	SD	df	t	p	Remark
Urban	274	3.42	0.53	382	2.78	0.001	Significant
Rural	110	3.02	0.74				

Table 6 shows the result of an independent samples t-test, which was used to compare urban and rural consumers in the acceptance of packaged food products in Delta State. The result shows that there is a significant difference between in the acceptance of packaged food products between urban and rural consumers in Delta State ($t [382] = 2.78$; $p < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the acceptance of packaged food products between urban and rural consumers in Delta State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products and their acceptance among consumers in Delta State

Table 7: Pearsons' Correlation analysis of the relationship between attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products and their acceptance among consumers in Delta State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	p	Remark
Attitude	384	3.19	0.52	0.659	0.434	43.4	0.000	Significant
Acceptance		3.33	0.60					

In Table 7, the researchers presented the result of a Pearson's correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the relationship between attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products and their acceptance among consumers in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.659$, $r^2 = 0.434$, $r^2\% = 43.4$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means that there is a significant relationship between attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products and their acceptance among consumers in Delta State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between educational level and their acceptance of made-in-Nigeria foods among consumers in Delta State

Table 8: Pearsons' Correlation analysis of the relationship between educational level and their acceptance of made-in-Nigeria foods among consumers in Delta State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	p	Remark
Educational Level	384	4.08	1.33	0.199	0.040	4.0	0.001	Significant
Acceptance		3.33	0.60					

In Table 8, the researchers presented the result of a Pearson’s correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the relationship between educational level and their acceptance of made-in-Nigeria foods among consumers in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.199$, $r^2 = 0.040$, $r^2\% = 4.0$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means that there is a significant relationship between educational level and their acceptance of made-in-Nigeria foods among consumers in Delta State.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between gender and acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products among consumers in Delta State

Table 9: Pearsons’ Correlation analysis of the relationship between Gender and acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products among consumers in Delta State

Variable	<i>n</i>	Mean	SD	<i>r</i>	r^2	$r^2\%$	<i>p</i>	Remark
Gender		1.67	0.47					
Acceptance	384	3.33	0.60	0.066	0.004	0.4	0.282	Not Significant

In Table 9, the researchers presented the result of a Pearson’s correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to examine the relationship between gender and acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products among consumers in Delta State. The result shows that $r = 0.066$, $r^2 = 0.004$, $r^2\% = 0.4$, $p > 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, which means that there is no significant relationship between gender and acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products among consumers in Delta State.

Discussion

The first finding showed that the extent to which Nigeria packaged food products are acceptable to consumers in Delta State is high. Various reasons could be responsible for this finding. For instance, the sheer presence and variety of Nigerian-made packaged foods on store shelves suggests a significant consumer base. Established brands like Dangote, Chivita, Bigi, and Golden Penny have achieved widespread recognition. Local companies like Indomie noodles have become dominant players in their categories, indicating strong consumer preference.

The above finding is in line with the result of past researches. For instance, according to Achumba et al. (2019), several Nigerian packaged food companies have achieved significant success, indicating consumer trust. Indomie noodles, Dangote products, and companies like Seven-Up bottling company are well-established, demonstrating consumer acceptance. The finding also supports Okonkwo (2023), who found that A growing sense of national pride and a desire to support local businesses can lead to a preference for domestic products. The finding is however, at variance with Onyemelukwe and Agbo (2018) and Anyaegbu and Onuorah (2017), who found that some consumers perceive a quality gap between imported and domestic products, attributing it to factors like outdated technology or inconsistent safety standards.

The second finding revealed that attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products can influence consumers’ acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products contributes 43.4% variability to consumers’

acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. This finding suggests that consumers' attitudes towards Nigeria packaged food products significantly influence their acceptance of these products. A corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between attitude towards Nigeria packaged food products and their acceptance among consumers in Delta State.

This finding underscores the importance of understanding consumers' perceptions, beliefs, and feelings towards locally produced packaged foods. Attitude encompasses consumers' overall evaluations, preferences, and emotional responses towards products. Positive attitudes towards made-in-Nigeria packaged foods may stem from factors such as perceived quality, trust in local brands, patriotic sentiments, and alignment with cultural preferences.

Consumers who hold favourable attitudes towards these products are more likely to perceive them as trustworthy, reliable, and desirable choices. They may value the use of locally sourced ingredients, support for domestic industries, and the contribution to the local economy. Moreover, positive attitudes towards made-in-Nigeria packaged foods may be reinforced by positive past experiences, word-of-mouth recommendations, and marketing efforts that highlight the unique benefits of these products. On the other hand, negative attitudes towards made-in-Nigeria packaged foods can hinder consumer acceptance. Factors such as concerns about product quality, safety, or perceived inferiority compared to imported alternatives may influence attitudes negatively. Additionally, past negative experiences, misinformation, or stereotypes about local products can contribute to unfavourable attitudes.

The above finding agrees with Sheth et al. (2019), who found that consumers with a favourable perception of locally made packaged foods are more likely to view them positively, trust their quality, and ultimately choose them over imported alternatives. The finding is also in line with Alegeh and Ogundipe, (2020), whose finding suggests that consumers with concerns about quality, safety standards, or outdated manufacturing processes might be less likely to choose domestic products.

The third finding showed that location can influence consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Location contributes 7.3% variability to consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. A corresponding hypothesis showed that there is a significant difference in the acceptance of packaged food products between urban and rural consumers in Delta State. Urban consumers appear to accept Nigeria packaged food products more than their rural counterparts. This finding suggests that the location where consumers reside can have a significant impact on their acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products. This finding underscores the importance of understanding regional preferences, cultural differences, and socio-economic factors in shaping consumer behaviour.

One key factor influencing consumer acceptance is cultural relevance. Different regions within Nigeria have diverse culinary traditions, taste preferences, and dietary habits. Therefore, packaged foods that align with local tastes and preferences are more likely to be accepted. For example, products that cater to traditional dishes or use familiar ingredients may resonate more

with consumers in specific regions. Moreover, socio-economic factors such as income levels and access to resources can influence consumer acceptance. In urban areas with higher purchasing power, consumers may prioritize factors such as convenience, health consciousness, and product innovation. On the other hand, consumers in rural or lower-income areas may prioritize affordability, familiarity, and basic nutritional needs.

Additionally, infrastructure and distribution channels vary across regions, impacting the availability and accessibility of packaged foods. Urban centres typically have well-established retail networks, supermarkets, and convenience stores, offering a wide variety of packaged foods. In contrast, rural areas may have limited access to such outlets, relying more on traditional markets or smaller shops. Therefore, the availability of Nigeria packaged food products may differ based on location, influencing consumer acceptance.

Cultural perceptions of product origin and quality also play a role. In some regions, there may be a preference for imported goods perceived as higher quality or more prestigious. However, efforts to promote the "Buy Nigerian" campaign and highlight the quality and benefits of locally produced foods are gradually shifting consumer attitudes towards domestic products. Furthermore, marketing and promotional strategies need to be tailored to specific regions to effectively reach and resonate with target consumers. Messaging that emphasizes local sourcing, authenticity, and community impact may be more effective in certain regions compared to others.

The above finding agrees with Anyaegbu and Onuorah (2017), who found that consumers in urban areas with wider access to imported products might be less familiar with or have less exposure to local brands compared to those in rural areas where domestic products might be more readily available. The finding also agrees with the finding of Ifeanyi (2014), which revealed that consumers in a region known for a specific food product might be more likely to trust and accept locally made versions of that product.

The fourth finding revealed that educational level can influence consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Educational level contributes 4.0% variability to consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. A corresponding hypothesis showed that there is a significant relationship between educational level and their acceptance of made-in-Nigeria foods among consumers in Delta State. This finding underscores the intricate relationship between education and consumer behaviour, shedding light on how socio-economic factors shape purchasing decisions. Individuals with higher levels of education often exhibit a more sophisticated understanding of food quality, safety standards, and nutritional value. They tend to be more discerning in their evaluations, scrutinizing factors such as ingredient sourcing, manufacturing processes, and adherence to quality control measures. Consequently, they may harbour reservations or scepticism towards locally-produced packaged foods, particularly if they perceive them to fall short of established quality benchmarks.

Moreover, higher education levels are often associated with greater exposure to diverse culinary experiences and global food trends. This exposure can broaden consumers' palates and

preferences, influencing their willingness to experiment with new products and flavours. However, it may also raise their expectations regarding product variety, innovation, and adherence to international standards, potentially impacting their acceptance of domestic food offerings. Conversely, individuals with lower levels of education may be more inclined to prioritize factors such as affordability, convenience, and familiarity when making purchasing decisions. They may exhibit greater loyalty to locally-produced goods, viewing them as a source of national pride and economic support for domestic industries. Additionally, limited access to education and information resources may restrict their ability to critically evaluate product quality, leading to greater reliance on brand reputation and marketing appeals.

The above finding is in line with Yildiz (2014), who found that higher education can equip consumers with better information processing skills and a more critical approach to product evaluation. This can lead to a greater emphasis on factors like ingredients, safety standards, and production processes. The finding also aligns with the finding of Alegeh and Ogundipe (2020), which shows that consumers with higher education might be more likely to research and compare products, potentially leading them to question the quality perception gap sometimes associated with domestic products. The finding also agrees with Ozoro and Ikeagu (2014), who found that higher education can expose individuals to a wider range of products and brands, including those from international markets. This exposure can influence preferences and create a perception of imported goods being superior.

The fifth finding showed that gender can barely influence consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Gender only contributes 0.4% variability to consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. A corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is no significant relationship between gender and acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products among consumers in Delta State. This finding implies that gender has no influence on consumers' acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products. Traditionally, gender has often been considered a critical determinant in consumer preferences, with stereotypes suggesting that men and women have distinct tastes and priorities. However, this finding challenges such assumptions, indicating that when it comes to accepting domestically-produced packaged foods, gender plays a minimal role.

This lack of gender disparity in acceptance could be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the increasing globalization of food markets has led to greater exposure to diverse culinary influences, eroding traditional gender-based food preferences. Additionally, socioeconomic factors such as income level and education might exert stronger influences on consumer behaviour than gender alone. Individuals from different genders may share similar concerns regarding product quality, safety, and nutritional value, overriding any gender-specific biases. Moreover, the evolving role of women in society and the workforce may contribute to a blurring of traditional gender roles, including food purchasing and consumption patterns. As women increasingly participate in the workforce and assume greater decision-making responsibilities within households, their preferences may align more closely with those traditionally associated with men, leading to convergence in acceptance levels of packaged

food products. Furthermore, cultural shifts and changing perceptions of domestically-produced goods may also play a role in neutralizing gender differences in acceptance. As national pride and support for local industries become more salient factors in consumer decision-making, the gender divide in acceptance of made-in-Nigeria products may diminish.

The above finding supports the finding of Yildiz (2014), who found that higher education can equip consumers with a more critical approach to food choices, potentially diminishing any gender-based differences. The finding also agrees with the finding of Rahman et al. (2017), which revealed that in households with higher incomes, gender roles might be less rigid, with both partners influencing purchasing decisions. The finding however, is at variance with Fernandes et al. (2014), who found that women might be more likely to prioritize health and nutritional factors when making food choices, which could in turn, influence their perception of local vs. imported products, depending on perceived health benefits.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings presented, several conclusions can be drawn regarding the acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State. Firstly, the extent of consumer acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products in Delta State is notably high, suggesting a positive reception and demand for these items among the populace. Thirdly, consumer attitudes towards Nigeria packaged food products significantly influence their acceptance, highlighting the importance of perceptions and preferences in shaping purchasing decisions. Furthermore, location within Delta State can also influence consumer acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products, indicating potential variations in market dynamics and consumer behaviour across different regions. Additionally, educational level emerges as a factor influencing consumer acceptance, suggesting that awareness, knowledge, and perceptions about product quality and value may vary among different demographic groups. Gender, however, appears to have minimal influence on consumer acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products, indicating that acceptance is more broadly influenced by other factors such as attitudes and location.

Based on the above finding, the researchers recommended the following:

1. Invest in market research and consumer engagement initiatives to better understand and cater to the specific needs and preferences of consumers in Delta State, thereby sustaining and further enhancing their acceptance of Nigeria packaged food products.
2. Implement targeted marketing and educational campaigns to promote the benefits and quality of Nigeria packaged food products, aiming to positively influence consumer attitudes and perceptions towards these items.
3. Tailor marketing strategies and product offerings to suit the unique preferences and demands of consumers in different locations within Delta State, thereby maximizing acceptance and market penetration across various regions.
4. Develop educational materials and campaigns aimed at informing consumers of the nutritional value, safety, and quality of Nigeria packaged food products,

particularly targeting demographic groups with lower educational levels to increase awareness and acceptance.

5. While gender may have minimal impact on acceptance, it is essential to ensure that marketing efforts are inclusive and appeal to all genders, focusing instead on factors such as taste, convenience, and affordability to drive consumer acceptance.

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